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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the design and construction of an energy efficient automatic emergency fluorescent Lantern with Battery Monitoring and Protection Circuit. It was implemented by designing and constructing each constituent parts of the entire system. The steps entail the design and construction of the ferrite core transformer, the design and construction of the blocking oscillator circuit, the construction of the fluorescent lamp circuit, the design and construction of the step-down voltage transformer for the charging circuit and finally the design and construction of the 12volts battery charger after bread boarding. It automatically switches on to the battery without a single blink in illumination when there is power failure. It remains significantly stable while in operation with no humming from the transformer.

Keywords: blocking oscillator, ferrite core transformer, Charging circuit, step-down voltage, humming

1. INTRODUCTION

Since power failure is a common phenomenon in Nigeria, the need for an alternative source of illumination in our homes, workshops, offices etc. becomes a viable option. Worst of all they are not reliable as the batteries easily go bad due to overcharging and these batteries cannot be replaced as they are not in the market. The fluorescent tube rechargeable lanterns in the market are not reliable as most of them often fail when charging the battery or the battery becomes overcharged and cannot supply power to keep the fluorescent "ON". According to (Linda, 2002), Light Emitting Diode (LED) Lanterns are brighter and long lasting than fluorescent lantern because of the small d.c current they consume. In this design, we have decided to opt for a fluorescent lantern rather than LED lantern because of the availability of the fluorescent tube and the ease of replacement when it goes bad. Various circuit types are used to drive the fluorescent tube. (Johannes and Van,1985) Use D.C–A.C converter to drive the fluorescent tube but the inherent shortcomings of this method outweighs the advantages. (Wikipedia, 2011) Use electrical choke as a ballast to provide high voltage to ignite the fluorescent tube. This approach has gone anachronistic and is no longer common. There are other circuits which feature an impedance matching circuit and rely on stray capacitances between the primary and secondary windings of the transformer. According to (Adegbemile, 2008), the most reliable approach is the use of blocking oscillator which acts as an electronic ballast to generate the requisite high voltage to strike the fluorescent tube. This saves much energy and is much efficient (Glen, 2008). In this work a blocking oscillator is used. This work provides a rechargeable lantern with high power capability to drive a 40watts lantern unlike the conventional lanterns with 5watts capability. It is uncommon to come by lanterns with such rating. Secondly, this works provides a lantern that provides a relatively constant illumination for long duration than conventional lanterns; including 5watts fluorescent and LED lanterns. Thirdly, most conventional lanterns operate on 3 or 6volts but in this design the lantern operate on 12V d.c. Fourthly, most conventional lanterns are manually switched on when there is power outage but this one is automatically switched "ON" without any bleak in illumination. The outstanding contribution to knowledge is that this design incorporates a battery monitoring and protection circuit in contradiction to conventional lanterns that do not possess this feature and secondly no human intervention is required to switch to battery mode. When batteries are connected in parallel it can provide illumination for over five (5hrs) depending on the number of batteries. The block diagram of the 40watts

rechargeable fluorescent lantern is shown in figure 1. It features a battery charger, a battery charge monitoring circuit, a switching circuit, a regulating circuit, a blocking oscillator, an inverter and a 40watts fluorescent tube.

Figure 1.0: Block diagram of a 40 watts rechargeable lantern

2. DESIGN CONSIDERATION

The emergency rechargeable lantern comprises several units. Each of the units was designed and tested. All the units were interconnected and tested for the desired performance. Two transformers were designed-one for the charging circuit and the other for the blocking oscillator. The battery over-charge protection circuit is shown in figure 3 while the oscillator circuit is shown in figure 4. The complete circuit is shown in figure 5. By designing and implementing each of the circuit and interconnecting them the complete work can be implemented.

2.1 Design of Transformer for Charging Circuit

The initial charging current of the battery is assumed to be between 8A.

Assumptions:

Battery Voltage =14Volts.

$$V_{d.c} = \frac{2V_p}{\pi} \quad (1.0)$$

The peak voltage is

$$V_p = \frac{V_{d.c} * \pi}{2} = \frac{14 * 3.142}{2} = 21.994$$

$$V_{rms} = \frac{V_p}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{21.994}{1.414} = 15.554 = 16V$$

Mains voltage = 220V,

Secondary current, Is = 8A

Transformer core has 64 laminations, each of 0.5mm thickness while the width of each lamination is 32mm. Cross-sectional Area, A of Core = 0.5*64*32 = 32*32 = 1024mm²

Since the input voltage is sinusoidal, the r.m.s value of the input voltage according is;

$$E_{rms} = \frac{2\pi f N A B_{peak}}{\sqrt{2}} \approx 4.44 f N A B \quad (1.1)$$

- Flux density of =1.2 T,
- Frequency =50Hz,
- N =Number of turns

From eqn. (1.1) r.m.s voltage, for N turns is

$$E_{rms} = 4.44 * 50 * N * 1.2 * 1024 * 10^{-6} = 0.2727 * N \text{Volts}$$

For a single Turn, $E_{r.m.s} = 0.2727 \text{Volts}$

Thus, Volt per Turn = 0.2727Volts.

Turns per Volt = $1/0.2727 = 3.66 \text{Volts}$.

Number of turns for primary winding of transformer = $220 * 3.66 = 806 \text{Turns}$.

Secondary voltage = 16V and Number of turns for Secondary winding = $16 * 3.66 = 58.58 \text{Turns}$

Since, secondary current = 8A, the transformer power rating in Volt-Ampere = $8 * 16 = 128 \text{VA}$ assuming no eddy current and iron losses in the core and windings.

It is not possible to achieve 100 percent transformation efficiency, therefore, assumed transformer rating = 250VA.

The transformer turn's ratio is

$$\frac{V_P}{V_S} = \frac{I_S}{I_P} \quad (1.2)$$

Thus,

$$I_P = \frac{V_S * I_S}{V_P} = \frac{16 * 8}{220} = 0.58 = 0.6 \text{A}$$

According to (Rajiv, 2011) Current density of copper wire = 3A/mm^2

$$\delta = \frac{I_P}{A_P}, \quad (1.3)$$

2.2 Selection of Wire Size for Primary and Secondary Winding

Primary winding Cross-sectional area,

$$A_p = \frac{I_P}{\delta} = \frac{0.6}{3} = 0.2 \text{mm}^2$$

$$A = \frac{\pi * d * d}{4}$$

$$d = \sqrt{4 * \frac{0.2}{\pi}} = 0.3 \text{ mm}$$

• A_p = Cross-sectional Area of the Primary Winding
Secondary Winding Cross-sectional area,

$$A_s = \frac{I_p}{\delta} = \frac{8}{3} = 2.7 \text{ mm}^2$$

$$d = \sqrt{4 * \frac{2.7}{\pi}} = 1.8 \text{ mm}$$

From table of Standard wire gauge (SWG),

- Primary winding = SWG 28,
 - Secondary windings = SWG 15.
- See figure 2 for Primary and Secondary windings

Figure 2: Step-down transformer

2.3 Selection of Component for Charger Unit

The bridge rectifier I.C of type DF04S was chosen.

From (FairChild Semiconductor, 2010), Peak Inverse Voltage of Bridge Rectifier (PIV) = 400V
and r.m.s Reverse voltage = 280V

The filter capacitor should handle twice the peak voltage (Muhammad, 2004).

Maximum capacitor voltage is between 1.5 to 3-times Peak Voltage

$$V_{cap} = \frac{1.5 * V_m}{2} \quad (1.4)$$

And the R.M.S voltage is 16Volts

$$\text{Therefore, } V_{cap} = \frac{1.5 * 16 * 2 * 1.414}{2} = 33 \text{ Volts}$$

A capacitor of 35Volts rating was selected

2.4 Selection of Capacitor Values

(Sen, 2004) Calculated the ripple voltage as:

$$V_r = \frac{I_{d.c}}{2fc} \quad (1.5)$$

Where V_r = ripple voltage,

- frequency = 50Hz and C is capacitance value
- $I_{d.c}$ = Charging or load current

Assuming a charging current of 1Amps,

$$V_r = \frac{I_{d.c}}{2 * 50 * C}$$

A ripple factor of 5 percent is used

$$0.05 = \frac{V_r}{V_{d.c}}$$

$$V_{d.c} = 2 * \frac{V_{max}}{\pi} = \frac{2 * 16 * 1.44}{\pi} = 14.6$$

$$V_r = 0.05 * 14.6 = 0.73$$

$$C = \frac{1}{2 * 50 * 0.73} = \frac{1}{73} = 14285 \mu f$$

A 1000 μ f/ 35V capacitor was selected

3. DESIGN OF BATTERY MONITORING CIRCUIT

A Zener diode, D7 of value 6.8V was selected.

$$R_4 = \frac{(V_{IN} - V_Z)}{I_{ZM} - I_{L(MN)}} \quad (1.6)$$

- V_{in} = battery voltage (14V), while V_Z is the Zener breakdown voltage. We assumed a minimum load current is 0A. Then,

$$R_4 = \frac{(14 - 6.8)V}{(133 - 0)mA} = \frac{7.2V}{133mA} = 0.0541k\Omega$$

Maximum resistance for $R_4 = 54\Omega$.

For a time constant of 100ms, we choose C_2 to be 100 μ f /25V.

$$R_5 = \frac{100 * 10^{-3}}{100 * 10^{-6}} = 1000\Omega = 1k\Omega$$

$$R_2 = \frac{(V_{in} - V_D)}{I_F}, \quad (1.7)$$

$V_D = 0.7V$ and forward current, $I_F = 40mA$

$$R_2 = \frac{(14 - 0.7)}{40 * 10^{-3}} = 417\Omega$$

$R_1 = R_2 = 470\Omega$, $R_3 = R_4 = 390\Omega$.

Figure 3: Battery charger and monitoring circuit

4. DESIGN OF INVERTER CIRCUIT

The circuit diagram of the inverter is shown in figure 4.

- Battery voltage = 12V
- Power supply frequency = 50 KHz
- Resistance, R1 selected, is 180 Ω

A switching transistor TIP3055 was chosen. Maximum Output power needed is 40watts

The oscillation frequency is:

$$f_o = \frac{1}{R_1 C_2}, \quad C_2 = \frac{1}{180 * 50khz} = 1.111 * 10^{-7} = 111nF$$

We selected 100nf capacitor.

4.1 Design of Pulse Transformer

- Flux density = 0.03T, f = 50 KHz, voltage = 12V, Output voltage 500Volts
- If transformer efficiency is 80 percent, then

Input Power = Output Power / efficiency

$$P_{in} = \frac{(60 * 100)}{80} = 75watts$$

- P_{in} = Input power

Cross –sectional Area of the ferrite core

$$A = \frac{\pi D^2}{4}, \text{ And Diameter } D = 10\text{mm}$$

$$A = \frac{(\pi * 10 * 10 * 10^{-6})}{4} = 78.5 * 10^{-6} m^2$$

According to (Sen, 2004), flux in the core is not sinusoidal, average voltage

$$E_{avg} = \frac{2\pi f N A B_{peak}}{\sqrt{2}} \approx 4.0 f N A B_{peak} \quad (1.8)$$

$$E_{avg} = 4 * 50 * 10^3 * N * 78.5 * 10^{-6} * 0.03 = 471 * N * 10^{-3} \text{Volts}$$

$$E_{avg} = 4 * 50 * 10^3 * N * 78.5 * 10^{-6} * 0.03 = 471 * 1 * 10^{-3} \text{Volts} = 0.47V$$

Turn per volt= $1/0.47=2.13$ Volts.

The primary winding will have $12 * 2.13 = 4.6$ as the feedback winding, but we selected 60 turns in other to provide some resistance to the battery current and protect the transistor. And for the feedback winding, we selected 12 turns. For the secondary windings, we have $1000 * 0.47 = 470$ Turns. Where 1000V is the selected voltage to strike the tube and cause it to come on.

4.2 Selection of Wire Sizes for Primary, Secondary and Feedback Windings

- Id.c = 12A
- Current density = 3A/mm².

By (Rajiv, 2011), cross-sectional area of Primary winding,

$$A_p = \frac{I_p}{\delta} = \frac{12}{3} = 4.0\text{mm}^2$$

$$d_p = \sqrt{\frac{4 * A * 1}{\pi}} = \sqrt{\frac{4 * 4 * 1}{\pi}} = 2.25\text{mm}$$

Primary winding= SWG 13

Secondary current = P/V = (60/500) = 0.12A

$$A_{s_s} = \frac{I_s}{\delta} = \frac{0.12}{3} = 0.04\text{mm}^2$$

$$d_{s_s} = \frac{\sqrt{4 * 0.04}}{\pi} = 0.22\text{mm}$$

Secondary winding = SWG 34

Figure 4 - Inverter circuit

Figure 5: Complete circuit diagram of the 20 watts rechargeable fluorescent lantern

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The design and construction was successfully completed and tested for performance evaluation. The luminous flux emanating from the middle of the 20watts fluorescent tube was measured using a HTC LX-101A LUX Meter. The meter was positioned at the middle of the tube where illumination was highest. Measurement was taken in thirty minutes (30mins) intervals. The results are shown in table 1.

Table 1: Luminous Flux Measurement

Luminous Flux (lux)	1146	1143	1078	976	735	718	661	537	395
Time (min)	0	30	60	90	120	150	180	210	240

From table 1, it can be seen that the illumination remains fairly steady between 0 –to- 30 minutes and thereafter it starts falling gradually. Figure 5 is the plot of the luminous flux with time while the rechargeable lantern is on the battery mode. At 395 lux the brightness of the lantern is still relatively good for office and domestic use.

Figure 5: Variation of luminous flux with time in minutes

Also, the Rechargeable Lantern automatically switches to the battery mode when there is power failure and the light remains "ON" during this transition period. When the Lantern is fully charged, the charging circuit goes in to trickle charging as depicted by the light emitting diode (LED) which comes up when the battery becomes fully charged. Figure 6 shows the photo of the automatic emergency rechargeable lantern.

Figure 6: Photo of the completed Automatic Emergency Rechargeable Lantern

6. CONCLUSION

The design and construction of an energy efficient automatic emergency fluorescent Lantern with Battery Monitoring and Protection Circuit was discussed and presented in this paper. The design objectives were accomplished because the lantern can successfully provide a relatively good illumination for over three hours and the battery over-charge protection circuit prevents the battery from being over- charged. This is manifested by the light emitting diode (LED) which turned "ON" when the battery is fully charged. It automatically switches on to the battery mode with no human intervention and without a single bleak in illumination when there is power failure. It remains significantly stable while in operation with no humming from the input transformer.

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